

Successful Team Strategy in Winning Regional Head Candidate Pairs (A Study of the Sambas District Elections from 2011, 2015 and 2020)

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ABSTRACT

Successful team strategies in political campaigns involve various tactics and strategies designed to win voters' votes. Data Collection: Data collection through surveys and polls can help successful teams understand current issues that are important to voters and develop relevant campaign messages. Online Campaigns: Online campaigns have become more popular in modern political campaigns and can help successful teams build voter engagement and expand a campaign's reach. Live Campaigns: Live campaigns such as campaign tours, rallies, and candidate debates remain an important part of political campaigns and can help successful teams build relationships with voters and amplify campaign messages. Social Media: Social media can be a highly effective tool in modern political campaigns and can help successful teams build voter engagement, expand campaign reach, and amplify campaign messages. Positive Campaigns: Campaigns focusing on positive messages and a strong vision can help successful teams build strong support from voters. Assembling a Strong Team: A successful team of experienced people with different skills can help strengthen the campaign and ensure that the right strategies are used to win the election. Financial Management: Effective financial management can help successful teams maximize the use of resources and ensure that campaigns run smoothly.

INTRODUCTION

Pilkada is one of the democratic mechanisms for electing regional heads in Indonesia. In every regional election, candidate pairs need support from a reliable and effective success team to win the election (Arbi Sanit, 2016). Regional elections do require a solid and well-organized successful team. The success team has a very important role in winning the Pilkada because they are responsible for organizing campaign strategies, designing campaign messages and programs, as well as mobilizing public support for the candidate pairs they support. In regional elections, the success team must also be able to maintain good communication with candidate pairs, campaign teams, and volunteers who are members of the success team.

They must also be able to monitor the political, social, and economic situation in the area so they can adapt campaign strategies and programs to existing conditions. According to David Easton, political strategy is an effort to gain support from voters or certain groups in society. Political strategy also includes efforts to influence policy and the political direction taken (David Easton, 1988). In this case, the success or failure of the candidate pair depends on the performance of the successful team. Therefore, candidate pairs need to choose a successful team that is qualified and trustworthy to win the regional elections.

As happened in Sambas Regency, there was a Success Team that succeeded in winning the Sambas Regional Head Candidate Pair for 3 Periods with different candidate pairs. So it is interesting to research and discuss to explore further the strategies carried out. The Chairman of the Success Team is Mr. Anwari, S.Sos., M.Si who is the son of Sambas who achieved victory for every candidate managed by him. Starting from the 2011 Pilkada, the 2015 Pilkada, and the 2020 Pilkada, victories have crossed over time and Mr. Anwari has been the main witness to the winning journey of candidate pairs in these 3 regional elections in Sambas Regency.

In the 2011 regional elections in Sambas Regency, West Kalimantan Province, there were 5 pairs of candidates fighting to become Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas. The four candidate pairs are:

1. Dr. Hj. Juliarti Djuhardi Alwi, M.PH paired with Dr. Pabali Musa, M.Ag
2. Drs. H. Darwin Muhammad is paired with Darso
3. Ir. H. Prabasa Anantatur, MH paired with Ir. H. Hasanusi, MM
4. Drs. H. Tufitriandi, MM paired with H. Perden Firdaus, S.Sos
5. Drs. H. Munawar, M.Si paired with Dr. Bonefasius Bone

In this regional election, the candidate pair Dr. Hj. Juliarti Djuhardi Alwi, M.PH, and Dr. Pabali Musa, M.Ag managed to win the election with 85,782 votes. The candidate pair is Dr. Hj. Juliarti Djuhardi Alwi, M.PH, and Dr. Pabali Musa, M.Ag succeeded in winning the 2011 Sambas Regional Election by carrying out a work program that focused on improving community welfare, economic empowerment, and improving infrastructure in the area. Apart from that, this pair of candidates also succeeded in building good relationships with community leaders and political parties in the Sambas area, which supported their success in the Pilkada.

For the regional elections in Sambas in 2015, there were three pairs of candidates competing for the positions of Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas, namely pair number 1 was Tony Kurniadi who was paired with Eka Nurhayati, number 2 was Atbah Romin Suhaili who was paired with Hairiah, and number 2 Rank 3 is Juliarti Djuhardi who is paired with Hasanusi. After voting, candidate pair number 2, namely Atbah Romin Suhaili and Hairiah, succeeded in winning the Sambas Regional Election with 126,599 votes.

For the regional elections in Sambas in 2020, there are four pairs of candidates competing for the positions of Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas, namely pair number 1 is Heroaldi Djuhardi Alwi who is paired with Rubaeti Erlita, number 2 is Satono paired with Fahrur Rofi, serial number 3 is Helman Fachri who is paired with Darso and serial number 4 is Atbah Romin Suhaili who is paired with Hairiah. After voting, candidate pair number 2, namely Satono and Fahrur Rofi, succeeded in winning the 2020 Sambas Regional Election with 85,830 votes. Sambas Regency is one of the districts in West Kalimantan Province which held regional elections in 2010, 2015, and 2020.

During this period, there were pairs of candidates who succeeded in winning the regional elections and pairs of candidates who failed. This shows that there are effective and ineffective strategies carried out by the Success Team in winning candidate pairs in the regional elections in the Sambas Regency. Therefore, it is important to carry out research on the strategies of successful teams in winning regional head candidate pairs in the Sambas Regency Pilkada from 2010, 2015, and 2020. This research aims to provide a better understanding of what strategies are effective in winning the Pilkada in Sambas Regency, as well as providing recommendations that can be used by the success team for candidate pairs in the next Pilkada.

An effective communication strategy is an important factor in winning general elections, including the Regional Head Election. In a political context, communication strategy involves the use of appropriate messages and communication channels to influence voters' views and behavior. Expert opinion regarding effective communication strategies is that effective political communication must be able to meet the needs and expectations of voters and be able to reach the target audience appropriately. effective and efficient. This can be done using various techniques, such as clear and easy-to-understand messages, consistent campaigns, and the use of social media and information technology.

One effective approach in political communication strategy is to build good and close relationships with voters. This approach is carried out by knowing and understanding the needs and interests of voters, as well as providing solutions that suit the problems faced by the community. Political communication expert, Kathleen Hall Jamieson, in her book entitled "The Press Effect: Politicians, Journalists, and the Stories that Shape the Political World" states that it is important to consider three things in political communication strategies: authenticity, relevance, and accountability.

First, authenticity, namely ensuring that the message conveyed truly reflects the beliefs and values of the candidate and their success team. Second, relevance, namely ensuring that the message conveyed is relevant to the issues that are important to voters. Lastly, accountability, namely ensuring that the campaign is carried out transparently and openly, and takes into account input from the community. Another opinion from political communication expert, Doris Graber, in her book entitled "Mass Media and American Politics," states that an effective communication strategy must pay attention to factors Context factors that can influence the effectiveness of messages, such as community interests, current issues, and community trends and attitudes towards politics and government. Overall, an effective communication strategy in politics requires a good understanding of the target audience, as well as the right techniques and approaches in conveying messages and building relationships with the public.

Political communication experts also emphasize the importance of paying attention to contextual factors that can influence the effectiveness of messages and campaigns. Therefore, successful teams in regional elections need to consider appropriate communication strategies to increase their chances of winning the election. The views of several experts regarding the factors that make a political strategy successful in regional head elections:

1. According to Elizabeth Simorangkir, a political expert from the University of Indonesia, the key factor for successful political strategy in regional head elections is a good understanding of voter characteristics and preferences, as well as the ability to present messages and work programs that suit the needs and aspirations of voters (Elizabeth Simorangkir, 2018).
2. According to Arie Sujito, a lecturer at the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Gadjah Mada University, an important factor in political strategy is the candidate's ability to build political networks and coalitions with political parties and local elites who influence the area they will lead (Arie Sujito, 2016).
3. According to Siti Zuhro, a political observer from Airlangga University, the key factor in the success of the political strategy in regional head elections is the candidate's ability to communicate and build good relationships with the community, as well as showing an honest and sincere attitude in carrying out leadership duties (Siti Zuhro, 2016).
4. According to Adi Prayitno, a political observer from Sebelas Maret University, the key factors for the success of political strategies are creativity and innovation in conveying messages and work programs, as well as the ability to adapt strategies to the conditions and characteristics of the region to be led (Adi Prayitno, 2017).
5. According to Arbi Sanit, a political observer, and lecturer at the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Hasanuddin University, important factors in political strategy are the integrity and credibility of candidates, as well as the ability to build good relationships with the community and show commitment to the welfare of the community they lead (Arbi Sanite, 2019).

Success teams play a very important role in political strategy in regional head elections. The following are several things that the success team can do to maximize the success of political strategies in regional head elections:

1. Analyze voter characteristics and preferences: The success team must carry out a thorough analysis of the characteristics and preferences of voters in the areas that will be contested. By understanding voter characteristics and preferences, successful teams can develop more effective campaign strategies.
2. Prepare clear messages and work programs: The success team must help candidates formulate messages and work programs that are clear and easy to understand by the public. The message and work program must be on the needs and aspirations of the people in the area to be led.
3. Expanding political networks and coalitions: The success team must help candidates expand political networks and coalitions with political parties, local elites, and community figures who have influence in the area they will lead.
4. Pay attention to social media: Successful teams must pay attention to the use of social media as an effective campaign tool. The success team must help candidates develop content that is interesting and in line with voter preferences on social media.
5. Maintain good communication with the community: The success team must help the candidate maintain good communication with the community in the area they will lead. Candidates must be able to provide quick and accurate responses to various problems and community needs.
6. Monitor and evaluate campaign strategies: The success team must monitor and evaluate campaign strategies regularly. This evaluation can help the success team to adjust the campaign strategy if necessary, so that the campaign becomes more effective and successful.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Successful Team Strategy

According to Locke and Latham's goal-setting theory, teams that articulate specific and challenging goals tend to achieve higher performance, provided these objectives are well-communicated and accepted by team members. Clarity in mission and individual roles fosters alignment, contributing to overall team cohesion. Effective communication emerges as a cornerstone in successful team strategies. Teams that prioritize open and transparent communication exhibit enhanced collaboration, information sharing, and problem-solving capabilities. Hackman and Wageman emphasize the importance of boundary management, underscoring the need for effective communication within the team and with external stakeholders (Lampaki et al, 2018).

This emphasis on communication aligns with the understanding that information flow is pivotal for teams to adapt and respond to dynamic challenges. Diversity and inclusion have garnered attention as key factors influencing team success. Research by Cox and Blake suggests that diverse

teams, encompassing various skills, perspectives, and backgrounds, can outperform homogeneous teams when managed effectively (Vigoda et al, 2012).

Leveraging the strengths of diverse team members enhances creativity and problem-solving, contributing to a more innovative and adaptive team dynamic. Effective leadership emerges as a critical factor in team success. Transformational leadership, as proposed by Bass and Avolio, underscores the leader's role in inspiring and transforming the team. A leader who can motivate and guide team members effectively contributes significantly to goal attainment and fosters a positive organizational culture.

Conflict resolution strategies play a vital role in maintaining team cohesion. Conflicts are inevitable, but how they are managed influences team dynamics. The Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument provides a framework for understanding and navigating different conflict resolution styles, promoting constructive resolutions, and strengthening team relationships. Continuous learning and adaptability are recognized as essential elements in successful team strategies. Senge's concept of the "learning organization" emphasizes the significance of ongoing learning and adaptation at both individual and organizational levels (Shell, 2001).

In a rapidly changing business environment, teams that embrace a culture of learning are better equipped to navigate challenges and capitalize on emerging opportunities. Social cohesion and trust among team members are crucial for team effectiveness. Tuckman's stages of group development highlight the importance of building trust and cohesion throughout a team's life cycle (Muzaffarsyah, 2020).

High levels of trust contribute to a positive team environment, fostering collaboration, communication, and a shared commitment to goals. Recognition and rewards further contribute to successful team strategies. Herzberg's two-factor theory posits that factors such as recognition and achievement play a role in job satisfaction and motivation. Acknowledging and rewarding team members for their contributions enhances morale and motivation, contributing to sustained team success (Lampaki et al, 2018).

Elections

Elections are a critical component of democratic societies, representing the mechanism through which citizens express their political preferences and choose their representatives. A rich body of literature explores various facets of elections, including electoral systems, voter behavior, campaign strategies, and the impact of elections on governance. One key area of study in the literature is electoral systems. Different countries employ diverse electoral systems, such as first-past-the-post, proportional representation, or mixed systems (Gandhi et al, 2009).

Scholars analyze the strengths and weaknesses of these systems, examining their impact on representation, political stability, and the inclusivity of minority voices. For example, proportional representation systems are often praised for ensuring a more accurate reflection of voters' preferences in the

composition of legislative bodies. Voter behavior is another focal point in the literature on elections (Manin et al, 2019).

Researchers investigate the factors influencing voters, including socioeconomic status, political ideology, and candidate characteristics. The rational choice model and social identity theory are commonly used to understand how individuals make voting decisions. Additionally, the role of emotions and psychological factors in shaping voter behavior has gained attention, emphasizing the complex interplay of rational and emotional elements in the electoral process. Campaign strategies and communication tactics employed by political parties and candidates are extensively studied. The advent of new media and digital technologies has transformed the landscape of political campaigning (Gandhi et al, 2009).

Scholars analyze the effectiveness of campaign advertisements, the use of social media, and the impact of debates on voter opinions. The literature also delves into the ethical considerations surrounding campaign strategies, including issues related to misinformation, fake news, and the manipulation of public opinion. Elections have a profound impact on governance and policy outcomes, and this aspect is explored in the literature as well. The "mandate theory" posits that winning candidates derive a mandate from the electorate to implement their proposed policies. Researchers investigate how elected officials respond to electoral incentives and whether policy outcomes align with campaign promises (Key, 1955).

The literature also examines the role of elections in promoting accountability and transparency in government. The issue of electoral integrity is a recurrent theme in election literature. Scholars explore topics such as electoral fraud, voter suppression, and the role of election monitoring organizations. The credibility of elections is crucial for maintaining public trust in democratic institutions, and the literature offers insights into the measures that can enhance the integrity of electoral processes (Pomper, 1967).

METHODOLOGY

The research approach used in this research is a qualitative descriptive approach. Qualitative descriptive is a research method that utilizes qualitative data and is described descriptively. Qualitative descriptive research aims to obtain a general understanding of the social reality that is the focus of the research. This general understanding comes from the participant's perspective, not determined in advance by the researcher. Then, an analysis and deepening of these social realities is carried out, then a conclusion is drawn in the form of a general understanding regarding these realities (Ruslan, 2006: 213). Observation is a method used to observe directly through sensing a situation, process, condition, activity, and behavior which can be used by researchers as complementary data (J.A. Holstein and J.F. Gubrium, 1995:72). Observations that will be carried out include field observation activities at several related agencies and several mangrove forest areas.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

History of Sambas Regency

Sambas Regency has an area of 6,395.70 km² or 639,570 ha (4.36% of the area of West Kalimantan Province), which is a district located on the northernmost part of the west coast of the West Kalimantan province. Sambas Regency consists of 19 sub-districts and 2 sub-districts directly border the State of Malaysia (Sarawak), namely Paloh and Sajingan Besar sub-districts. Sambas Regency has various superior potentials that can be developed and offered to investors. The history of the Sambas Kingdom is related to the Majapahit Kingdom and the Banjar Sultanate. The Sambas Kingdom was then continued by the Sambas Sultanate whose origins cannot be separated from the kingdom in Brunei Darussalam.

These two kingdoms have very close fraternal relations. In ancient times, in the country of Brunei Darussalam, there was a king whose title was Sri Paduka Sultan Muhammad. After he died, the royal throne was handed over to his children and grandchildren for generations. The ninth descendant arrived, namely Sultan Abdul Djalil Akbar. According to the *Staatsblad van Nederlandisch Indië* in 1849, this region was included in the *zuid-ooster-afdeeling* based on the *Bêsluit van den Minister van Staat, Gouverneur Generaal van Nederlandsch-Indie*, on 27 August 1849.

Regional Boundaries

Sambas Regency is located between 1'23" N and 108'39" E with the following administrative regional boundaries:

1. The north borders Sarawak, East Malaysia
2. The east borders Bengkayang and Sarawak Regencies, East Malaysia
3. The south is bordered by Singkawang City and Bengkayang Regency
4. The west is bordered by the Karimata Strait and the South China Sea C.

Climate

Sambas Regency is a tropical climate area with an average monthly rainfall of 227.94 mm and an average number of rainy days of 11 days/month. The highest rainfall occurs from September to January and the lowest rainfall occurs between June and August. The average air temperature ranges from 22.9°C. Up to 31.05 °C. Air temperature the lowest 21.2 °C occurred in August and the highest 33.0 °C in July. Relative air humidity 81-90%, air pressure 1.001-1.01/Hm Bar, wind speed 155 - 173 km/day, sunlight election 50.73%, daily evaporation between 4.2-5.9 Hm and evapotranspiration monthly 134.7 - 171.4 mm.

Total Population

Based on data from the Sambas Regency Population and Civil Registration Service as of August 2013, the population of the Sambas Regency is 667,921 people. The total male population is 341,982 people (51%), while the female population is 325,939 people (49%). Population by age group (mid 2013):

1. 0 - 14 years by 26%.
2. 15 - 64 years old by 66%

3. 65 years and above by 8%

From these data, it can be concluded that the population of Sambas is dominated by people of productive age compared to people of non-productive age. The total population is based on age groups and gender with details of the total age group 0-9 years as many as 58,467 people (first largest), the total age group 0-4 years as many as 57,301 people (second largest), the total age group 10-14 as many as 52,607 people (third largest). The population density is around 78 people/km² or 2,724 people per village.

The distribution of population in Sambas Regency is not evenly distributed between one sub-district and another. Pemangkat District is the district with the highest population density, namely 403 people/km². On the other hand, Sajingan Besar District, with an area of around 21.75% of the total area of Sambas Regency, is only inhabited by 7 people/km². The population growth rate was 1.01 percent.

The population growth rate of Tangaran District is the highest compared to other sub-districts in Sambas Regency, namely 3.50 percent. Meanwhile, the lowest was South Javai District, namely -0.33 percent. Tebas District is in first place in terms of population, but in terms of population growth rate, it is still below the growth rate of Sambas Regency, namely 0.92 percent.

Tribes

The majority of the ethnic groups inhabiting Sambas are the Malay Sambas tribe who live in the coastal areas and downstream banks of the Sambas River. In several sub-district cities such as Pemangkat and Sambas City, there are Chinese people. In the interior or several areas bordering Bengkayang, the majority of Dayak people live, an example of a Dayak tribe that lives in this area is the Kanayatn Dayak tribe.

Economics

The economic structure of Sambas Regency is still dominated by 3 main sectors, namely the agricultural sector, the trade-hotel-restaurant sector, and the processing industry sector. The agricultural sector contributed 39.77%, the hotel-restaurant trade sector contributed 30.37% and the processing industry sector contributed 11.27% (in 2012). The inflation rate based on producer prices in 2012 in Sambas Regency decreased compared to 2011, namely from 7.26% to 5.41% in 2012.

The level of income of a region can be measured, among other things, from per capita income, land and building tax revenues (PBB), Regional Original Income (PAD) as well as a qualitative description of the condition of people's clothing, food, and housing. Based on 2003 data, the economic situation of Sambas Regency can be seen, namely:

1. PAD of Rp. 16,350,041,018,-
2. Per capita income is IDR. 3,419,922,-
3. Land and Building Tax (PBB) is IDR. 8,560,013,046,-
4. The regional minimum wage (UMR) is IDR 400,000
5. Meanwhile, the level of livelihood income according to the sector is:

6. Agriculture numbered 207,350 people
7. The Processing Industry numbers 152,028 people
8. Electricity, gas, and water amounted to 9,053 people
9. The building numbers 28,308 people
10. Trade totaled 34,695 people
11. Relationships amount to 2,874 people
12. Finance numbered 9,723 people
13. Other community services amounted to 34,678 people

Sambas Regency Regional Election

2011 Regional Elections

Since the Announcement dated 11 to 17 December 2010, Political Parties or Associations of Political Parties can register candidate pairs for Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas by submitting the candidate requirements to the KPU of Sambas Regency. Political parties can register candidate pairs if they meet the following requirements:

1. Obtaining a seat in the District DPRD member election. Sambas in 2009 had a minimum of 15% (fifteen percent) of the total seats in the District DPRD. Sambas with 45 (forty-five) seats, namely 7 seats;
2. Obtaining valid votes in the district DPRD member election. Sambas in 2009 was at least 15% (fifteen percent) of the accumulated valid votes in the district DPRD member elections. Sambas totaling 235,928 valid votes, is 35,389 valid votes, is 35,389 valid votes.

This is regulated in the District KPU decision. Sambas Number: 35 of 2010 concerning the number of Seats and the Number of Valid Votes for Political Parties Based on the Election Results for District DPRD Members. Sambas in the Context of Nominating Candidate Pairs for Regent and Deputy Regent in the 2011 Election for Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas. After researching the completeness and requirements of the candidates for Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas, the KPU of Sambas Regency determined 5 (five) pairs of candidates for Regent and Deputy Regent Sambas by the Sambas Regency KPU Decree Number 07 of 2011 concerning the Determination of Regent and Deputy Regent Candidate Pairs to be Participants in the 2011 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent Election.

The names of the Regent and Deputy Regent Candidate Pairs in the 2011 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent Election are as follows following:

1. Spouse Drs. H. Tufitriandi, MM and H. Perden Firdaus, S.Sos, supported by the Crescent Star Party, the Reform Star Party, the Reform Democracy Party, the Ulama National Awakening National Front Party, the Sovereignty Party, the Nusantara Republic Party, the National Democratic Party;
2. Spouse Dr. H.J. Juliarti Djuhardi Alwi, M.PH and DR. Pabali Musa, M.Ag, supported by the Democratic Party, National Mandate Party, United Development Party, National Party for the Indonesian People's Fortress;
3. Spouse Drs. H. Munawar, M.Si, and Dr. Bonefasius Bone;
4. Spouse Ir. H. Prabasa Anantatur, MH and Ir. H. Hasanusi, MM;
5. Spouse Drs. H. Darwin Muhammad and Darso.

2015 Regional Elections

In the 2015 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent Election, geographically Sambas Regency consisted of 19 sub-districts, 184 villages, and 1,115 polling stations. Participants in the 2006 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent Election were 3 (three) Candidate Pairs, namely:

1. The couple Tony Kursiadi, ST, M.Si and Hj. Eka Nurhayati, SE is a candidate pair for Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas from an individual candidate. On Sunday, July 26 2015 at 11.14 WIB, registered as a candidate pair for Regent and Deputy Regent of Sambas in 2015 by submitting the Nomination Requirements Documents and Candidate Requirements to the KPU of Sambas Regency. Candidate Pair Tony Kurniadi, ST, M.Si and Hj. Eka Nurhati, SE is supported by 63,366 people who meet the requirements;
2. The couple H. Atbah Romin Suhaili, Lc, and Hj. Hairiah, SH, MH, supported by the Prosperous Justice Party (4 seats), the Greater Indonesia Movement Party (5 seats), the People's Conscience Party (3 seats), and the United Development Party (4 seats). c. Spouse Dr. Hj. Juliarti Djuhardi Alwi, M.Ph and Ir. H. Hasanusi, MM, supported by the National Mandate Party (6 seats), the Indonesian Democratic Party of Struggle (6 seats), Parati NasDem (4 seats), the Democratic Party (4 seats), the Crescent Star Party (1 seat).

2020 Regional Election

Participants in the 2020 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent Election are 4 (four) Candidate Pairs nominated by political parties who have seats in the Sambas Regency DPRD, with a minimum requirement of 20% of the total number of seats or 25% of the valid votes from the total number of valid votes, that is :

1. Candidate Pair No. Sequence 1, namely H. Heroaldi Djuhardi Alwi, S.T, M.T and Hj. Rubaeti Erlita, S.Sos.I, S.H, supported by the National Awakening Party and the Golongan Karya Party;
2. Candidate Pair No. Sequence 2, namely H. Satono, S.Sos.I, M.H and Fahrur Rofi, S.I.P, M.H.Sc, supported by the Greater Indonesia Movement Party and the National Mandate Party;
3. Candidate Pair No. Rank 3, namely Dr. Helman Fachri, SE, M.M, and Darso, supported by the NasDem Party and the Indonesian Democratic Party of Struggle;
4. Candidate Pair No. Sequence 4, namely H. Atbah Romin Suhaili, LC, M.H and Hj. Hairiah, S.H., M.H, supported by the

Prosperous Justice Party, United Development Party, Democratic Party, and People's Conscience Party. The 2020 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent Election recorded a total Permanent Voter List of 427,926 people, consisting of 217,686 male voters and 210,240 female voters (Sambas Regency Strategic Plan, 2020-2024).

In the 2020 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent election, the Sambas Regency KPU determined the Elected candidate pair for Sambas Regent and

Deputy Regent, namely H. Satono, S.Sos.I, M.H and Fahrur Rofi, S.I.P, M.H.Sc in the 2020 Simultaneous Election with Number: 2/PL.02.7- Kpt/6101/KPU-Kab/I/2021 on January 22 2021 with a total of 85,830 (Eighty Five Thousand Eight Hundred and Thirty) votes or 30.61% (Thirty Point Sixty) One Percent) of the total valid votes. The number of Sambas Regency Community Participation in the 2020 Sambas Regent and Deputy Regent Election was 286,918 with a percentage of 66.707% of the total voter data of 430,120 voters.

Successful Team Strategy

The Regional Head Election (Pilkada) is a crucial moment in the life of Indonesian democracy. Amid fierce competition, successful teams have an important role in winning the hearts and votes of voters. A mature and measurable strategy is needed to achieve this goal. Data analysis and research are the main foundation of any successful campaign. Data on political preferences, local issues, and voter demographics are key to forming effective strategies. Surveys and interviews are important tools for understanding the needs and desires of potential voters. Identifying the voter base is the next step. Knowing which groups are most likely to support a candidate allows success teams to direct energy and resources more efficiently.

A clear and effective campaign message is the essence of a political campaign. The candidate's vision and mission must be conveyed firmly through various communication channels. This message must be relevant to people's needs and easy to understand. Social media has become a central pillar in modern political campaigns. A strong strategy on platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram can expand reach and increase public awareness of candidates. Even though social media has a big influence, campaigns on the ground still cannot be ignored.

Meetings with residents, community visits, and open events are effective ways to build personal connections with voters. A caring, personal approach and building relationships are key to winning support. Understanding voters' needs and aspirations and providing concrete solutions to the problems faced by society are important steps. Partnerships with other groups or individuals with influence can also broaden the voter base. Collaboration with external parties can help expand the campaign's reach. It is important to include the interests and needs of disabled and minority communities in campaign platforms. Building inclusive programs and supporting all levels of society is key to winning the trust and support of these groups.

Controversial issues are inevitable in political campaigns. Facing these issues honestly and transparently is an important step to winning voters' trust. Good coordination among successful team members is the key to running an effective campaign. Each team member must clearly understand their roles and responsibilities. Open and regular communication is the key to optimizing team performance. Regular training and development for successful team members is important. Skills such as effective communication, time management, and campaign strategy must be continuously improved. There is no guarantee that a political campaign will run without a hitch.

Therefore, successful teams must have contingency plans and clear actions to deal with unexpected situations. The ultimate goal of any political campaign is to encourage voters to get out and vote. The technique "Get Out The Vote" (GOTV) is a specific strategy designed to achieve this goal. This involves efforts to identify and contact potential voters. The Role of a Success Team In every Regional Head Election, the success team has a central role in supporting the candidate. They are solid pillars, working diligently and passionately to achieve victory. Voter mobilization is the main milestone of their work. With full dedication, they developed a strategy to invite the people to participate in the democratic process. From door to door, from village to village, they reach every level of society to ensure the people's voice is heard.

Not only that, the success team is also the meeting custodian and campaign event manager. They plan every step carefully, ensuring that every meeting is a valuable moment for the candidates to dialogue with the people. Behind the scenes, they craft sharp communication strategies, turning every word into a tool to win hearts and minds. Resource management is a tough task that is carried out with full responsibility. From funds to volunteer labor, everything is managed wisely. Every expense is calculated, and every favor is directed with a clear end goal in mind: victory. Their campaign message felt alive, etched in the hearts of every voter. A successful team is the architect behind inspiring words, words that bring new hope.

They understand the power of the message, and with passion, they convey it to the world. In times of crisis, they are a strong fortress. Crisis management is a test of their mettle. With cool heads and decisive action, they calmed the storm, ensuring that the journey to victory continued unwaveringly. Volunteers and fieldwork teams are their wings. They are recruited, trained, and energized to serve a common cause. Together, they became an unstoppable force, crisscrossing the country to ensure the people's voices were heard. Based on the results of the interview with Mr Anwari on July 4 2023 at 10.00 WIB, he is part of the Success Team which has succeeded in winning 3 (Three) Regent and Deputy Regent Candidate Pairs since 2011 in Sambas Regency said that Resource Management is an important part in determining the Role of the Success Team."Based on experience, there are two types of success teams, the first is the party success team and the second is the non-party success team. "The party success team is filled by the structural members of the party management, while the non-party success team is filled by community leaders, religious leaders, and community leaders who have the same vision and mission as the candidates put forward by the party," he said.

Data and analysis are their guide. They don't just rely on instinct, but also facts and figures. They monitor every change, understand political dynamics, and wisely, direct candidates towards a path of victory. On voting day, they were loyal witnesses. At each polling station, they ensure the process runs smoothly, fairly, and transparently. They are guardians of justice, ensuring the rights of every voter are respected. The success team is a pillar of strength in every regional election. They are a tireless army, carrying hopes and aspirations to bring about change. Behind a candidate's victory, some unknown heroes turn

the world of politics upside down for the common good. In the world of politics, the success team is the driving force behind every candidate's success in the regional elections.

They are figures who work tirelessly, with dedication and high enthusiasm, to ensure that the people's voices are heard and well represented. One of the main tasks of the success team is voter mobilization. They are the spearheads who are on the front lines, visiting homes, going to markets, and greeting people with a smile. They build personal relationships with the community, listen to aspirations, and explain the candidate's vision and mission with enthusiasm. Every village, every village, becomes a battleground where successful teams fight for support. However, the work of a successful team doesn't stop there. They are also responsible for managing campaign events. From large public meetings to small gatherings at the village office, every event is carefully organized. A careful rundown is prepared, facilities are well prepared, and the agenda is carried out promptly.

All of this is done to ensure that the candidate's message is conveyed clearly and effectively to the public. Resource management is also the main focus of successful teams. They must be smart in managing campaign funds, ensuring that every expenditure is in line with the priorities and strategies that have been set. In addition, they also coordinate fieldwork teams and volunteers, ensuring that everyone has a clear role and can contribute optimally. Campaign messages are the lifeblood of every political campaign. The successful team worked hard to formulate the right message, which was able to touch the hearts and minds of the people. They understand people's needs and desires and articulate them in simple but powerful words.

This message is then conveyed through various media, from television advertisements to roadside banners. Amid the ups and downs of a campaign, a successful team must also be ready to face a crisis. Unexpected situations can occur at any time, and they must be able to respond quickly and wisely. Effective communication, solid coordination, and strong leadership are the keys to overcoming any challenges that arise. Volunteers and fieldwork teams are trained soldiers of a successful team. These are individuals who volunteer their time and energy, with one common goal: winning for their candidates. A successful team must be able to recruit, train, and motivate this team so that they can work together as a solid unit. Data and analytics play an important role in guiding campaign strategy. Successful teams don't just rely on intuition but also check facts and figures.

They conduct surveys, analyze trends, and monitor local and national political developments. All of this is done to ensure that the campaign remains relevant and adaptive to changes in the political environment. On voting day, the success team was a loyal witness. They monitor each polling station, ensuring that the process runs smoothly and according to the rules.

They also provide help and support to voters who need it, ensuring that every vote is counted correctly. Mr. Anwari the Success Team who has won several Regional Head Elections in Sambas Regency also added that there is a division of success teams to focus on winning in the Regional Election

contestation."The party success team is also called Team Think, which is a team that comes from several proposing parties and has the function of formulating strategies and planning strategic steps to win the proposed candidate," he said. In every step of the journey to victory, a successful team is the main pillar of support.

They are the unknown heroes who work behind the scenes, with sheer determination and passion, to turn hope into reality. With their every step and action, they lead the candidate towards the path of victory, towards a better future for society. They are pillars of strength in the world of politics, and candidate success cannot be realized without them.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The title of this research discusses the team's strategy in winning regional head candidate pairs in the regional elections in Sambas Regency from 2011, 2015, and 2020. Based on this research, several important things can be concluded:

1. **Team Strategy Has a Significant Influence:** Research shows that team strategy plays an important role in the success of regional head candidate pairs. Factors such as organization, communication, mass mobilization, and campaigns are key elements in a successful team strategy.
2. **Continuity and Learning:** The analysis of three consecutive regional elections (2011, 2015, and 2020) makes it possible to identify patterns and trends in the team's strategy. This allows teams to learn from previous experiences and adapt their strategies according to local needs and political dynamics.
3. **The Importance of Adapting to Local Context:** Each regional election has different political characteristics and dynamics. Therefore, a successful strategy team must be able to adapt their approach to the specific conditions and needs of Sambas District.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research on the topic is still needed "Successful Team Strategy In Winning Regional Head Candidate Pairs (A Study Of The Sambas District Elections From 2011, 2015 And 2020)."

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